

**ASSESSMENT OF ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES AND
FRUIT QUALITY OF PAPAYA BREEDING LINES**

A THESIS

BY

MD. JAHID HOSSAIN

MASTER OF SCIENCE

IN

GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING

BANGABANDHU SHEIKH MUJIBUR RAHMAN AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY

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MD. JAHID HOSSAIN

Registration no. 2016-05-3835

Certificate of Approval:

(Prof. Dr. Nasrin Akter Ivy)

Major Professor and Chairman

Advisory Committee

(Prof. Dr. Md. Golam Rasul)

Member

Advisory Committee

(Prof. Dr. Md. Ahiduzzaman)

Member

Advisory Committee

Dedicated

To

My Beloved Parents, My Mentors

and

Them Who's Happiness Relate

with My Success

ABSTRACT

ASSESSMENT OF ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES AND FRUIT QUALITY OF PAPAYA BREEDING LINES

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Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) is enriched with vitamins, minerals and antioxidant properties, hence its intake and improvement is essential. The experiment was conducted to study the performance of antioxidant properties and fruit quality of different papaya breeding lines at BSMRAU. A total of 25 papaya breeding lines were evaluated on 11 morphological and fruit quality characteristics. Among them BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) showed uniform and medium plant height and girth, where CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9) showed the tallest plant height and girth. Supreme fruit weight (1.2 kg) was observed in BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) followed by CP003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8) and BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3). Fruit yield of BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) was recorded as (22.7±8.1 kg/plant) and upmost yield was observed (28.9±13.4kg/plant) in CP 0015 (3 × 5). The highest TSS was observed (9.9±0.7) in BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (15×16) followed by BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) is (9.2±0.3). Among the breeding lines, ten selected lines were evaluated on six antioxidant properties and exhibited significant genotypic differences. BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) showed the highest ascorbic acid (64.3±6.0 mg/100 ml), phenolic compounds (37.9±1.3 mg gallic acid equivalents/100g) and antioxidant activity (3.6±0.5 µmol AAE/g). BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3) contained the maximum flavonoid content (27.1±2.3 mg catechin equivalents/100g). BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16) showed the highest lycopene content (6.4±1.2 mg/100g). Positive correlation found in yield with fruit quality and negative with antioxidant properties. The significant variation in antioxidant properties and fruit quality clearly showed the potential value of selected papaya breeding lines as new cultivars and parents in future breeding programme.

Keywords: Papaya, fruit quality, antioxidant, ascorbic acid, carotenoids.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) is a tropical fruit plant having a small, sparsely branched tree and all parts of the plant contain latex in articulated laticifers (Heywood *et al.*, 2007). It is originated in Southern Mexico and Costa Rica; subsequently it was introduced as a plantation crop in Australia, Philippines, Hawaii, South Africa, Sri Lanka, India and in all tropical regions (Krishna *et al.*, 2008). The wild forms of *Carica papaya* are believed to have in south of Mexico and were introduced into western hemisphere and tropical areas during the early Fifteen Centuries (Ferraó, 1992). Papayas are dioecious. There are three basic flower types in domesticated plants such as: a. Female flowers, b. male flower, c. bisexual flowers. The morphology of inflorescences and flowers varies with the sex of the tree (Khuspe and Ugale, 1977). Some agricultural varieties are gynodioecious- their trees are either hermaphrodite or female. Papaya usually grown from seed. It can also be propagated vegetatively using leafy stem cuttings (Magdalita *et al.* 1984). Papaya is now cultivated worldwide in tropical and subtropical climates mainly for its melon-like fruit which has worldwide acceptance as fruit and as well as vegetable. In Bangladesh average per hectare yield were maximum at Jashore (62MT) followed by Rajshahi (55MT), Tangail (54MT) and Bandarban (52MT) (Moniruzzaman *et al.*, 2019).

Papaya is available throughout the year and it is powerhouse of nutrients (Appendix I). It is a rich source of carotenoids and excellent source of vitamins that are powerful antioxidants (Aravind *et al.*, 2013). Papaya fruit also contains minerals, magnesium and potassium; the B vitamin pantothenic acid and folate and fiber. In addition to all this, it contains a digestive enzyme-papain effectively treats causes of trauma, allergies and sports injuries. All the nutrients of papaya as a whole improve cardiovascular system, protect against heart diseases, heart attacks, strokes and prevent colon cancer.

Consumption of guava and papaya fruits reduced oxidative stress and altered lipid profiles. Thus, it could reduce the risk of diseases caused by free radical activities such as cancer, and cardiovascular disease (Krishna *et al.* 2008). Consuming papaya regularly will ensure a good supply of vitamin A and C which is essential for good health especially for eyesight. Fruit quality of papaya made an impact on consumer's preferences. There are several fruit quality traits that differ the papaya breeding lines from one to another like fruit weight, fruit diameter, fruit pulp thickness, fruit pulp color and total soluble solids. Fruit weight and number of fruit quality impact on the fruit yield (Ara *et al.*, 2016). Fruit pulp color of papaya could be yellow, reddish to red. Fruit pulp color differ the quality not only nutritionally but also consumer's preference. Total soluble solids (TSS) are an important parameter of fruit quality. TSS states the amount of soluble solids in liquid. TSS value affects the taste of the fruit because it can indicate the level of sweetness of the fruit (Kusumiyati *et al.*, 2020).

Now a day there is an increasing interest in the selection of crops with higher antioxidant contents. Phenolic and flavonoid compounds and lycopene are effective antioxidants, while β -carotene is a precursor of vitamin A. They have become widely studied due to their free-radical scavenging properties which confer them potentially beneficial properties to human health (Cheng *et al.*,1997). Antioxidants are chemical compounds that can bind to free oxygen radicals preventing these radicals from damaging healthy cells whereas pro-antioxidant act indirectly either by modulation of direct agents or by regulation of the biosynthesis of antioxidant proteins (Halliwell, 2011). Papaya also has traditional and modern medical and dental uses.: fruits, seeds, latex and extracts have been used for treating at least forty human conditions (Amanat Ali.*et al.*, 2002).

Epidemiological studies have shown that many of these antioxidant compounds found in papaya possess anti-inflammatory, antiatherosclerotic, antitumor, antimutagenic, anti-carcinogenic, antibacterial, to a greater or lesser extent (Pe' rez-mature *et al.*, 2009).

The information regarding genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance provide the basis for selection in any fruit trait that contribute to yield, facilitate selection of suitable parents (Nirujogi *et al.*, 2012). Again, positive genetic correlation between two desirable traits makes the job of the plant breeder easy for improving both traits simultaneously (Mahesh *et al.*, 2015). Path coefficient analysis helps to find out the direct and indirect contribution from each of the characters. Several studies have reported the relationship between fruit quality and the antioxidant content of different fruits, for instance, the correlation of the fruit size and antioxidant contents of guava (Srimat *et al.*, 2014), internal fruit color and carotenoid contents of mango (Gardea *et al.*, 2008), and flesh color and lycopene content of tomato (Arias *et al.*, 2000). The knowledge of the relationship between fruit quality traits and antioxidants is a useful tool to estimate one trait will have an effect on another trait and so it can be used for indirect selection. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken with following objectives:

1. To find out the morphological characteristics of papaya breeding lines.
2. To evaluate antioxidant compounds and fruit quality of papaya breeding lines
3. To determine a correlation between quality characters of papaya lines and
4. To identify the lines high in antioxidants with good fruit quality for using as new commercial cultivars or parents for a future papaya breeding program.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Currently, there is an increasing interest in the selection of crops with higher antioxidant contents. Papaya is a good source of antioxidant contents along with several vitamins. Relevant information available in the literature pertaining to characterization, variability, correlation and path coefficient of the papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) breeding lines were reviewed in this chapter. But unfortunately there are nominal literature, regarding the studies in the country. However, the available literatures related to the present studies have been reviewed under the following heading.

2.1 History and origin of papaya

Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.), a kind of tropical evergreen fruit tree originated from Mexico and Central America, is mainly found distributed in the south of China, such as Hainan, Guangdong, Guangxi, Yunnan, Taiwan, and Fujian Province. Starley *et al.*, (1990) mentioned in their study that province is the optimum region to cultivate papaya in China. Singh (1990) stated that papaya is native in the north-tropical western hemisphere. Some have suggested a center of origin in Central America or the South Mexico. Manshardt and Zee (1994) found wild papayas (exclusively dioecious) in the Caribbean costal low lands of southern Mexico and northern hemisphere. Mc Vaugh and Anderson (2001) mentioned in their study that *Carica papaya* L. (only cultivated species under Caricaceae family) along with two other genera *Horovizia* and *Jarilla* of the family has their wild form in Mexico and Guatemala. Moreover, papaya was found under cultivation in the Spanish Conquest Central America and Mexica. Allen *et al.* (2002) reported that papaya was probably domesticated in northern tropical America but a precise region has not been determined. Papaya is now cultivated worldwide in tropical and sub-tropical climates.

2.2 Biology of Papaya

Papaya is a semi-woody, usually single-stemmed plant, widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions. The plant is singular in several aspects: short-lived perennial growth habit, large palmate leaves, rapid growth, hollow stems, petioles and fruits, and high phenotypic plasticity. Jiménez *et al.* (2013) declared that papaya plants may have three possible sexual forms: female, male, and hermaphroditic. Additionally, alterations in sexual forms and flower structure have been related to environmental constraints, which consequently modify fruit production and morphology, respectively.

Arumuganathan *et al.* (1991) mentioned that papaya is a dicotyledonous, polygamous (having male, female or hermaphrodite flowers on the same plant), diploid species with a small genome of 372 Mbp/1C and nine pairs of chromosomes.

Kabir *et al.* (2001) evaluated 10 papaya lines (P001, P003, P023, P040, P043, P061, P063, P091 and variety Shahi) for their performance in Gazipur, Bangladesh during October 1994 to September 1995. They reported that the lines varied significantly for plant height up to female flower initiation which ranged from 52.7cm to 71.4 cm. The lines also varied greatly regarding base girth throughout the growth period.

An experiment was conducted by Faten and Bakry (2005) during two consecutive years on papaya cultivars Solo. They found that the average plant height, stem diameter at 10 cm above the soil and petiole length of the studied cultivars was 125.0 cm, 7.00 cm and 20.67 cm, respectively.

Schweiggert *et al.* (2012) conducted an experiment and found that papaya is commercially propagated by seed. Seeds from hermaphrodite trees always segregate into hermaphrodites and females at the ratio of 2:1 and the sex types of the plants can be determined only by inspection of the flowers. Therefore, it is a general practice for farmers to plant three to five seedlings in one hill, allowing them to grow for 4 to 6 months until the sex types are

identified, and then to remove the undesired plants to develop the orchards with only hermaphrodite plants. Because hermaphrodite fruits contain small cavity with higher edible meso-carp. Thus it has a greater preference by farmers and consumers. But continuous selection of these plants for succeeding generation causes inbreeding depression.

2.3 Morphological Characterization of Papaya

Germplasm characterization is essential to utilize and improve plant genetic resources in various breeding programs. It can be done using morphological and biochemical traits. Morphological analysis is the basis for any crop improvement program.

Kaluram *et al.* (2018) stated that papaya genotype shows moderate to high phenotypic divergence. But divergence in flower and fruit characteristics are more desirable for commercial utilization. Anitha *et al.* (2018) studied that the fruit is oval to round nearly pyriform or elongated club shaped, 15-50cm long.

Timon *et al.* (2017) worked on Papaya germplasm could be separated morphologically based on either vegetative or yield contributing characters. However, yield related traits were more reliable because, they permitted to describe the considerable amount of variation. But the combination of both aspects will give a perfect view of the difference. A study showed by Silva *et al.* (2017) found that some of the morphological traits were highly heritable and thus making selection easy. These are plant height, pulp thickness, fruit diameter and fruit length. Iamjud *et al.* (2013) conducted an experiment and found that the highest TSS value belonged to PML (15%) and the lowest content of TSS was recorded in KD2 and SKK (11%). Parmeshwar *et al.* (2015) worked on papaya fruit flesh color and found that papaya fruit flesh color may vary among yellow, orange and red color. And there was significant difference in TSS and other compounds in papaya fruits. Flesh color also affect the biochemical properties of the papaya fruits.

Brown *et al.* (2012) investigated the variation occurs due to diverged source of germplasm or due to differential sex types in papaya. Papaya plants showed an extensive range of variation in vegetative and productive traits based on their sex types. Female plants showed significant diversity in flower, fruit shape, central cavity, seed color while male plants were more divergent in inflorescence size.

Asudi *et al.* (2010) found a considerable variation in morphological traits like fruit size, fruit color, flesh color, tree habit in the germplasm of different localities in Kenya. Fruits of papaya showed the maximum amount of variation among all morphological traits.

An experiment was carried out at Fruit Research Station, Binodpur, Rajshahi during the period from January 2009 to February 2010 with ten papaya lines by Biswas *et al.* (2010). They reported that Shahi variety of papaya produced the maximum number of fruits (45.8) plant⁻¹ followed by HRCP-2 (45.0) and the minimum number of fruits plant⁻¹ (19.1) was counted in HRCP-7. The highest fruit yield plant⁻¹ was produced by HRCP-2 (73.13 kg) followed by Shahi pepe (62.52 kg) while it was the lowest (35.20 kg plant⁻¹) in HRCP-7. The TSS content varied from 8 to 12%. The line HRCP-8 produced the longest fruit (22.6 cm) and it was the shortest (17.5cm) in Shahi. Breadth of fruit was maximum (52.3 cm) in HRCP-5 and minimum (49.0 cm) was recorded in HRCP-9 and Shahi. Cavity breadth ranged from 7.5 to 12.1cm.

An experiment conducted by Jaime *et al.* (2007) stated that immature fruit which was green in color contained white latex in more amount on ripening process fruits skin starts turning yellow, orange color to red, becomes aromatic, juicy and sweet.

Ram *et al.* (1999) made fifteen varietal crosses between five papaya cultivars as female and three cultivars as male to evaluate them for their yield and other component traits. They reported that Ramnagar yielded the maximum of 32.5 kg/plant followed by Pusa Majesty (25.9 kg), Homestead (22.8 kg) and Pusa Delicious (20.0 kg).

Sunrise solo and Waimanalo yielded the lowest. Among the hybrids, none yielded better than Ramnagar local. The number of fruits plant⁻¹ was the maximum in two varieties viz. Ramnagar local and Homestead, but Pusa Majesty and Pusa Delicious had higher fruit weight. Based on fruit yield plant⁻¹ and fruit number, hybrid between Pusa Delicious and Ramnagar local, and Pusa Majesty and Ramnagar local were considered promising.

Wagh *et al.* (1992) conducted an experiment on fourteen papaya varieties to assess fruits on performance and physico-chemical characters. They noted that the maximum average fruit weight was observed in Pusa Majesty (1780 g) and the minimum in Sunrise Solo (347 g). The maximum fruit length was observed in Thailand (29 cm), while the lowest fruit length was observed in Sunrise Solo (12.3 cm). The maximum fruit girth was observed in Pusa Majesty and the lowest in sunrise Solo. Significantly highest flesh thickness was observed in Co-2 (4.0 cm), while it was the lowest in Solo and Sunrise Solo (1.8 cm). The differences in width of central cavity were non-significant. The maximum width of cavity was observed in Co-5 (9.0 cm) and the minimum in Sunrise Solo (4.9 cm). And they found that Solo produced the maximum number of fruits (47.44 plant⁻¹) while Thailand produced the minimum number of fruits (18.319 plant⁻¹). Pusa Delicious recorded the maximum weight of fruit (44.80 kg plant⁻¹) while Solo recorded the minimum (15.90 kg/plant).

A study was conducted by Ghanta and Mandal (1992) on genotypic variability and correlation co-efficient relating to fruit yield and few other quantitative characters with seven papaya cultivars. They reported that the fruit yield of the studied cultivars ranged from 18.67 to 34.00 kg/plant with a mean of 27.25 kg/plant.

Mekako and Nakasone (1975) indicated that the time from the emergency of the floral button to the anthesis of the flower, under the conditions in Hawaii, was of approximately 45 days in masculine flowers and 47 days in the feminine, whereas the hermaphrodite's floral types delayed to 49days.

2.4 Bio-chemical Characterization of Papaya

Papaya is a lozenge tropical fruit, often seen in orange-red, yellow-green and yellow-orange hues, with a rich orange pulp. The fruit is not just delicious and healthy, but whole plant parts, fruit, roots, bark, peel, seeds and pulp are also known to have medicinal properties. Papaya is a powerhouse of nutrients (Appendix 1).

Kritsanee Iamjuda *et al.* (2016) showed the ascorbic acid content, total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, antioxidant activity, lycopene, and β -carotene in ripe papaya fruits of nine selected S3 papaya breeding lines revealed significant differences ($p < 0.01$) (Table 3). The variation of antioxidants is essential for improving new papaya cultivars with high antioxidants and carotenoids.

Srimat *et al.* (2014) have reported the relationship between fruit quality and the antioxidant content of different fruits, for instance, the correlation of the fruit size and antioxidant contents of guava.

Aravind *et al.* (2013) showed that papaya is a rich source of three powerful antioxidant vitamin C, vitamin A and vitamin E; the minerals, magnesium and potassium; the B vitamin pantothenic acid and folate and fiber. *Carica papaya* can be used for treatment of a numerous diseases like warts, corns, sinuses, eczema, cutaneous tubercles, glandular tumors, blood pressure, dyspepsia, constipation, amenorrhoea, general debility, expel worms and stimulate reproductive organs and many, as a result *Carica papaya* can be regarded as a Nutraceutical. Accordingly, Iamjud *et al.* (2013) demonstrated a difference of growth and fruit quality of 7 'Khaek Dam' papayas. This study showed clearly distinct amount of antioxidant. Bhowmik *et al.* (2013), suggest that diets high in carotenoid pigments were associated with a reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases, prostate cancer, and lung cancer. Papaya (*Carica papaya*) fruit is a good source of carotenoids and an excellent source of vitamins that are powerful antioxidants.

According to Barreto *et al.* (2009) There are several fruits such as pequia, star palm nut and golden spoon showed the highest levels of total phenolic and flavonoids content. There is the highest level of total carotenoids. They confirmed the high positive correlation between free radical scavenger activity and phenolic compounds and flavonoids contents. Gardea *et al.* (2008) reported the relationship between internal fruit color and carotenoid contents of mango. Presence of more carotenoid content in mango make the fruits color more deep yellow to orange.

The study of Lacerda *et al.* (2004) reported that ascorbic acid (vitamin C) has many biological functions and plays an important role as an antioxidant, preventing cell damages caused by oxidation.

According to the literature, several authors also reported high correlation between free radical scavenger activity and total phenols (Chun *et al* 2003). There is high correlation between total phenols and free radical scavenger activity which was observed by Luximon-Ramm

The study of Arias *et al.* (2000) showed there was a significant correlation between flesh color and lycopene content of tomato. Tomato with higher lycopene were more red then others. Currently, there is an increasing interest in the selection of crops with higher antioxidant contents. Phenolic and flavonoid compounds and lycopene are effective antioxidants, while β -carotene is a precursor of vitamin A. They have become widely studied due to their free-radical scavenging properties which confer them potentially beneficial properties to human health.

CHAPTER III

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Morphological Characterization

3.1.1 Location of the experimental site

The experiment was conducted at the research field (Fig. 01) of Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University (BSMRAU), Salna, Gazipur during February 2020 to August 2021. The location of the site was about 40 km North of Dhaka city and 10 km north to Gazipur with 24.09⁰ N latitude and 90.26⁰ E longitude an elevation of 8.40 m from the sea level. Previously it was under ‘Shal’ Forest and subsequently was developed for research purpose.

Fig. 01. Research field view of the experiment at fruiting stage

3.1.2. Climate and soil

The experimental site was situated in the subtropical zone, characterized by heavy rainfall during the month of May to September (appendix II) and scanty rainfall during the rest of the year. The average annual rainfall is about 2100 mm, most of which occurs in short spells during June to October. The hottest months are in summer (March to May) and winter is short and cool whereas temperature during the monsoon season is moderate. The soil of the experimental field was clay loam in texture and acidic in nature having a pH of around 5.8

with poor fertility status. It belongs to the Salna soil series of “Shallow Red Brown Terrace” under Madhupur tract (Brammer and Brinkman, 1977).

3.1.3 Experimental Materials

Twenty-five papaya breeding lines were used in this experiment (Table 01). The female flowers were crossed with hermaphrodite flowers and the breeding lines were developed.

Table 01: List of the 25 papaya breeding lines.

Sl no.	Genotype	Sl no.	Genotype
1	BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7)	15	BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (13 × 18)
2	BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (6 × 3)	16	BU papaya-1(1) (11 × 10) (15 × 16)
3	BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3)	17	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 9) (13 × 14)
4	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 9) (5 × 1)	18	BU papaya-1(1) (7 × 6) (11 × 10)
5	BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16)	19	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 4)
6	CP 005 (1 × 6) (4 × 6)	20	CP 0012 (7 × 2) (10 × 11)
7	BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 3)	21	BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 9)
8	CP 005 (7 × 6) (4 × 6)	22	CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9)
9	CP 003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8)	23	CP 001 (13 × 12) (6 × 7)
10	CP 0015 (3 × 5)	24	CP 0014 (11 × 2) (6 × 2)
11	BU papaya-1(1) (6 × 3)	25	BU papaya-1(1) (4 × 2) (5 × 2)
12	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 3)		
13	CP 005 (11 × 6) (9 × 6)		
14	CP 0013 (3 × 2) (4 × 2)		

3.1.4 Experimental Design

Experiment was carried out in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications.

3.1.5 Land Preparation

The experimental plots were prepared ploughing followed by harrowing and laddering to bring the desired tilth. Beds for each entry containing pits were raised with 15 cm and developed properly. Drains between beds were maintained. Final land and bed preparation was done about one week before transplanting. The pit size was (50 ×50×50) cm.

3.1.6 Application of Manure and Fertilizers

Fertilizers were applied per pit at the following rate:

Cow dung	:	12-15 kg
Urea	:	250-300 g
TSP	:	200-250g
MP	:	300-350 g

Well decomposed cow dung was applied during the final land preparation. Total TSP, MP and half of the Urea were applied in the pit 10 to 15 days prior to the seedling transplantation. The rest of the urea was applied one month after transplantation (Fertilizer Recommendation Guide- 2018).

Mode of Application:

1. The basal was applied in pit 10-15 days before planting seedlings and mixed thoroughly with soil followed by irrigation.
2. The first top dressing of N and K was done around the plant after 30 days of seedling establishment and mixed thoroughly with the soil followed by irrigation.
3. The remaining N and K fertilizers were applied around the plants at 30 days interval at the rate 25g/plant up to flowering and 50g/plant until two months before final harvest for both the nutrients and mixed thoroughly with the soil followed by irrigation.

3.1.7 Raising of Seedlings

Seeds of all the twenty-five papaya breeding lines were sown in 19th February, 2020 in pot (Fig. 02). The seedlings were emerged 15 to 18 days after sowing. After germination the young seedlings of 2-3 days old were transplanted into polythene bag (size: 15 cm x 10 cm), containing a mixture of soil and well decomposed cow dung (1:1). Both the soil of pot and bag were sterilized by using 40% formaldehyde solution.

3.1.8 Transplanting of Seedlings

For transplanting of papaya seedlings of the experiment, pits were prepared. In each pit, only one seedling of 45 days old was transplanted on 12th April 2020.

3.1.9 Gap Filling

Within one week after transplanting several seedlings were found dead. The seedlings were replaced by the other seedlings of the same genotype.

3.1.10 After Care

The growing plants were individually supported by a 2m long bamboo sticks to prevent lodging. Cultural operations was done properly. Irrigation was given seven days' interval. Insecticides, growth hormone, fungicides were spread. Fungicide named autostin (50g in 10 liter of water) was applied after one week of transplantation to prevent stem rot. All the measures were taken to ensure proper growth of papaya plant.

3.1.11 Data Collection

Morphological data were collected from 25 papaya breeding lines on following traits-

Fig. 02: Data collection in the experimental field

Fig. 03: Life cycle of papaya from seed to seed

Plant Characters

1. Days to first flowering: Measured from transplanting to days to first flower appearance.
2. Plant height (cm): Measured from the ground to top of the plant.
3. Plant girth (cm): It was measured by estimating the girth 10 cm above the ground.
4. Distance from fruiting node (cm): Measured from the ground to the stalk of the first fruit.
5. Fruits per plant: Fruits were counted manually at fruiting period.
6. Fruit yield (kg/plant): Mean value of fruits multiply with fruit weight per plant.

Flower Character

Different types of flowers were observed (Fig. 04)

➤ Type of flower

- a. Male
- b. Female
- c. Hermaphrodite

Male

Female

Hermaphrodite

Fig. 04. Types of flowers found in different papaya breeding lines

➤ Types of flowering

- a. Solitary
- b. Inflorescence

Solitary

Inflorescence

Fig. 05. Flowering types in different papaya breeding lines

Fruit Characters

Quantitative character of fruits

Data was collected from five fruits /plant.

- Fruit length (cm). Fruit lengths of ten fruits were measured from base to tip of fruit.
- Fruit diameter (cm). Mean value of ten fruits were recorded at the broadest part.
- Individual fruit weight per plant (kg): Weight of ten fruits was recorded.
- Fruit pulp thickness (cm): Fruit pulp thickness of ten fruits was measured with rind.
- Fruit cavity (cc): Fruit was cut and length and width of the cavity of ten papayas were recorded.
- Fruit pulp color: Pulp color of ripe fruits was recorded yellow, deep yellow to orange and red
- Total Soluble Solid (%): Recorded by hand refractometer and average of ten fruits.
- Average fruit weight (kg): The yield per plant was recorded from the total harvested fruits and was expressed in kilogram (kg).

Mean of the recorded data was calculated

3.2 Biochemical Characterization

3.2.1 Experimental site

The biochemical characterization was conducted during July 2021 to August 2021. It was done in the laboratory of Department of Agro-processing of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University, Gazipur-1706.

Fig. 06. Laboratory view of the experiment at biochemical analysis

3.2.2 Plant materials

Fruits were harvested from both female and hermaphrodite plant of ten selected papaya breeding lines {(BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3), BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16), CP 001 (13 × 12) (6 × 7), CP 003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8), CP 005 (1 × 6) (4 × 6), BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 4), BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7), BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (6 × 3), CP 0015 (3 × 5) and BU papaya-1(1) (11 × 10) (15 × 16)} at the research field of Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University (BSMRAU), Salna, Gazipur-1706. Fruits were harvested at 25% skin yellow, a commercial maturity stage harvesting index that can function as quality standards for ripe consumption papaya (Santamaría Basulto *et al.*, 2009).

Fig. 07: Biochemical analysis in the laboratory

3.2.3 Determination of total antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity was determined by the ferric reducing/antioxidant power (FRAP) method (Benzie and Strain, 1996).

Plant sample extraction procedure

For antioxidant activity determination 3 g of each papaya flesh central part were homogenized in 20 ml of methanol using an Ultra-Turrax homogenizer (T25, Ika Works Inc., USA). The homogenates were then centrifuged at 3900g for 20 min. The supernatant was recovered and stored at -20 °C until analysis.

Chemicals required

- FRAP solution
- Methanol and ascorbic acid

Preparation of FRAP solution

The FRAP solution was prepared daily by mixing 25 ml of 300 mM acetate buffer (pH 3.6), 2.5 ml TPTZ solution (10 mM in 40 mM HCl), and 2.5 ml of 20 mM FeCl₃.6H₂O solution.

Preparation of ascorbic acid (ASA) standards

0.02 g of ascorbic acid was dissolved in 20 ml of distilled water (DW) to get a stock solution (SS) of 1000 µg/ml. Then, standard series were prepared as follows-

000.0 µl SS+ 1000 µg DW=00.0 µg/ml

100.0 µl SS+900.0 µl DW=100 µg/ml

200.0 µl SS+800.0 µl DW=200 µg/ml

300.0 µl SS+800.0 µl DW=300 µg/ml

400.0 µl SS+600.0 µl DW=400 µg/ml

500.0 µl SS+200.0 µl DW=500 µg/ml

Assay for antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity was determined by the ferric reducing/antioxidant power (FRAP) method. The FRAP solution was warmed at 37°C for 30 minutes in an incubator before use.

75 µl flesh extract was mixed with 75 µl methanol.

2850 µl of warmed FRAP solution added and mixed well in vortex.

The mixer was allowed to react at 37°C for 60 minutes in incubator.

Then the absorbance was measured at $\lambda=593$ nm using spectrophotometer, methanol was used as blank.

Calculations

The antioxidant activity of each fruit extract was calculated and standards as the percentage inhibition.

Fig. 08: Calibration curve of ascorbic acid (ASA) standards

From the calibration curve of the standards was prepared and equation found that,

$y = 0.3412x + 0.0158$; Here, y = absorbance and x = concentration (unknown)

The antioxidant activity (µg/g FW) was expressed as µmol ascorbic acid equivalents (AAE)

3.2.4 Determination of Total Phenolic Content

Total phenolic content was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Swain *et al.*, 1959).

Chemical required

- 0.25 N Folin-Ciocalteu reagents
- 1 N Na₂CO₃
- Gallic acid

Preparation of 0.25N Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent

12.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent was added with distilled water and value made 100 ml.

Preparation of 1N Na₂CO₃ solution

1.06 g Na₂CO₃ was added into 20 ml of distilled water for the preparation of 1N Na₂CO₃ solution.

Preparation of Gallic acid standards

0.02 g (20 mg) of Gallic acid was dissolved in 20 ml of DW to get a stock solution (SS) of 1000 µg/ml. Then, series of standards were prepared as follows-

000.0 µl SS+ 1000 µg DW=00.0 µg/ml

10.00 µl SS+990.0 µl DW=10 µg/ml

20.0 µl SS+980.0 µl DW=20.0 µg/ml

40.0 µl SS+960.0 µl DW=40.0 µg/ml

100.0 µl SS+900.0 µl DW=100 µg/ml

200.0 µl SS+800.0 µl DW=200 µg/ml

Assay for phenolic content

Determination of total phenolic content spectrophotometrically according to the folin-Ciocalteu method.

150 µl of flesh extract was mixed with 2400 µl of distilled water and 150 µl of 0.25 N Folin-Ciocalteu reagents. Then mixed well by using a vortex ((Vortex-2 genie, USA)

The mixtures were allowed to react for 3 min and then 300 µl of 1 N Na₂CO₃ solution was added and mixed well.

The solution was incubated at room temperature (25 °C) in a dark condition for 2 h.

Then the absorbance was measured at 725 nm using a spectrophotometer (T80 UV-Vis spectrometer, PG Instruments, USA).

Calculations

A calibration curve was prepared from the standards and equation found that,

Fig. 09: Calibration curve of Gallic acid standards

$y = 0.0244x - 0.0661$; Here, y = absorbance and x = concentration (unknown)

The phenolic content (µg/g FW) was expressed as gallic acid equivalent. expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/100 g fresh weight (FW).

3.2.5 Determination of Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content was assessed by colorimetric assay (Zhishen *et al.*, 1999).

Chemicals required

- 5% Sodium nitrite (NaNO_2)
- 10% Aluminum chloride (AlCl_3)
- 1 M Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Catechin

Preparation of 5% Sodium nitrite (NaNO_2)

5 g of NaNO_2 was dissolved in distilled water and the volume was made 100 ml.

Preparation of 10% Aluminum chloride (AlCl_3)

10 g of AlCl_3 was dissolved in distilled water and the volume was made 100 ml.

Preparation of 1M Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)

40 g of NaOH was dissolved in distilled water and the volume was made 1 L.

Preparation of Catechin standards

0.02 g of Catechin was dissolved in 20 ml methanol to get a stock solution (SS) of

1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Then, standard series were prepared as follows-

000.0 μl SS+ 1000 μg DW=00.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

25.00 μl SS+975.0 μl DW=25.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 50.00 μl SS+950.0 μl DW=50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

100.0 μl SS+900.0 μl DW=100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

200.0 μl SS+800.0 μl DW=200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

400.0 μl SS+600.0 μl DW=400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

800.0 μl SS+200.0 μl DW=800 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Assay for Flavonoid content

Total flavonoid content was assessed by colorimetric assay.

One ml of flesh extract was mixed with 4 ml of dH₂O and then stood for 5 min.

Then 0.3 ml of 5% NaNO₂ and 0.3 ml of 10% AlCl₃ were added and mixed well with the Vortex and stood for another 6 min.

Added two ml of 1 M NaOH were added and diluted to 10 ml with dH₂O.

Then The mixture was measured immediately at 725 nm using the spectrophotometer.

Calculations

A calibration curve was prepared from the standards and equation found that,

Fig. 10: Calibration curve of Catechin standards

$y = 0.0011x + 0.0102$; Here, y = absorbance and x = concentration (unknown)

Total flavonoid content was expressed as mg catechin equivalents (CE)/100 g FW.

3.2.6 Determination of lycopene and carotenoids

Chemical Required

Hexane; Ethanol; Acetone

Procedure

For lycopene and β -carotene, 0.2 g of each papaya pulp (central part) were homogenized in 20 ml of solvent hexane: ethanol: acetone at 2:1:1.

Three ml of water were added and stood for 15 min to cause a phase separation.

The upper hexane phase content was measured to determine the absorbance at 444 and 503 nm using a spectrophotometer (Genesys 10S UV-Vis, Thermo Scientific, USA).

Calculation

The contents (mg/100 g FW) of both lycopene and β -carotene were calculated according to

$$C_{ly} = (6.95A_{503} - 1.59A_{444}) (0.55) (537) (V/W)/10,$$

$$C_{\beta c} = (9.38A_{444} - 6.70A_{503}) (0.55) (537) (V/W)/10,$$

respectively, where 0.55 is the ratio of the final hexane layer volume to the volume of mixed solvents added, 537 is the molecular weights of lycopene and β -carotene (g/mol) W (mg) is the weight of papaya tissue analyzed, V (ml) is the volume of mixed solvents added, and 10 is for the adjustment to mg/100 g units.

3.2.7 Determination of Ascorbic acid content

Ascorbic acid content (mg/100 ml) in juice directly extracted from flesh at the fruit midpoint was measured using the 2,6-dichloroindophenol titrimetric method (Helrich *et al.*, 1990).

Apparatus

- Conical flask
- Volume flask
- Morter and pestle
- Burette
- Pipette
- Filter paper etc.

Reagent

- 3% Meta Phosphoric acid solution.
- Dye solution.
- Standard ascorbic acid solution.

Sample preparation

As papaya fruit flesh is semi-solid or solid product, 10g of papaya fruit flesh was blended with 3% HPO₃ and then made up to 100ml and filtered.

Preparation of 3% Meta Phosphoric acid solution

30 gm metaphosphoric acid was added with 80 ml glacial acetic acid and made the volume 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of Dye solution

250 gm of 2,6-dichloroindophenol was dissolved in approximately 150 ml of hot distilled water containing 42 mg of sodium bicarbonate. Then cooled and diluted with distilled water to 200 ml and stored the solution in brown bottle to store at 3⁰C.

Standard ascorbic acid solution

100 mg of L-ascorbic acid was dissolved in a small volume of 3% metaphosphoric acid solution and made up to 100 ml with same solution. Then 10 ml of this stock solution was diluted to 100 ml with 3% metaphosphoric acid (0.1 mg ascorbic acid per ml).

Assay for Ascorbic acid content

Determination of ascorbic acid content using the 2,6-dichloroindophenol titrimetric method. 5 ml of standard ascorbic acid solution was diluted with 5 ml of 3% metaphosphoric acid. Then diluted solution was titrated with dye solution till pink color persisted for 10 seconds. The dye factor mg ascorbic acid per ml of dye was calculated. Then titration was done as follows, 10 ml of filtered pipette was taken into a conical flask and was titrated with standard dye solution to a pink end point.

Calculation

$$\text{Dye factor (DF)} = \frac{\text{Ascorbic acid present in the solution titrate}}{\text{titre(volume of dye)}}$$

$$\text{Ascorbic acid } \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{100\text{g}}\right) = \frac{\text{Titre} \times \text{Dye Factor} \times \text{Volume made up} \times 100}{\text{Volume of filtered taken} \times \text{wt. or volume of sample taken}}$$

3.2.8 Statistical Analysis

The experimental data obtained on various selected variables was analyzed by the standard method of statistical analysis of RCBD. Statistical analysis was done by taking the mean value of five plants from each genotype in each replication. Two-way analysis of individual character was done for each characters using the mean value and was estimated using statistic- 10 computer program. Mean, Co-efficient of variation (CV %), Standard deviation (SD), co-variance was also estimated using R software. All data were expressed in mean \pm standard deviation. ANOVA was performed. The means were separated using Bonferroni test at 0.05 level. Linear relationships among data were analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r).

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) is an important fruit and vegetable crop. It is a rich source of carotenoids and excellent source of vitamins that are powerful antioxidants. Considering these aspects and importance of papaya, the present study has been initiated. The findings of the present study have been discussed below under different parameters studied. Morphological analyses were carried out on 25 papaya breeding lines at the experimental field of Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding and the biochemical analysis was carried out at the laboratory of Department of Agro-processing BSMRAU. Specific findings presented in table (02 to 08) and figure (10 to 15).

4.1 Morphological Characterization

4.1.1 Plant characters

Plant Height

In first flowering stage plant height of papaya plants were recorded the highest in CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9) (117.0±8.0 cm), and the lowest plant height in BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 9) (73.3± 6.8 cm) (Table 02). BU papaya-1(1) (2×7) and BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9 × 3) showed medium plant height, (98.3±4.5) and (99.3±5.7) respectively. The average height among the papaya breeding line was recorded (91.9±13.3) cm. Maximum plants height growth were attained in the first flowering stage of the papaya plants. The distribution of morphological traits of different papaya breeding lines has shown in Figure 11. Magdalita *et al.* (1984) conducted phenotypic variability studies on 100 genotypes in Philippines and showed that plant height at first flower stage ranged from 80.00cm to 208.83 cm among the studied genotypes. Faten and Bakry (2005) found the average plant height (120 cm) in cultivars solo for two consecutive years

Table 02: Mean performance of morphological traits of different papaya breeding lines.

SL. No.	Entry	Plant Height (cm)	Plant Girth (cm)	Distance of Fruiting Node(cm)	No. of Fruit per Plant	Yield per Plant (kg/plant)
1	BU papaya-1(1) (2×7)	98.3±4.5	17.6±0.6	4.3±0.6	19.0±1.0	22.7±8.1
2	BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (6 × 3)	89±4.04	15.6±0.6	4.0±1.0	20.0±2.0	19.6±11.7
3	BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9 × 3)	99.3±5.7	18.3±0.6	5.3±0.6	17.7±2.5	20.2±5.6
4	BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (5 × 1)	111.3±6.8	18±0.0	5.0±0.0	20.0±1.0	18.6±0.6
5	BU papaya-1(1)(1×10)(15×16)	108.3±8.6	18±1.0	4.7±0.6	16.7±1.5	10.6 ±1.1
6	CP 005 (1 × 6) (4 × 6)	92±2.6	15±0.6	5.0±0.0	23.3±1.5	15.3±4.9
7	BU papaya-1(1) (12×7) (4 × 3)	108.7±2.5	17.7±0.6	5.3±0.6	18.7±1.2	16.3±2.8
8	CP 005 (7 × 6) (4 × 6)	93.0±4.6	15.7±0.6	4.7±0.6	19.7±1.2	23.7±6.4
9	CP 003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8)	107±6.0	17±1.0	5.7±0.6	19.7±4.5	17.7±1.3
10	CP 0015 (3 × 5)	98.3±5.0	17±0.0	5.3±0.6	22.0±1.0	28.9±13.4
11	BU papaya-1(1) (6 × 3)	91.3±5.0	17.7±0.6	4.0±0.0	15.7±2.0	9.0±1.2
12	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 3)	103.0±7.6	15.5±0.6	4.7±0.6	24.7±1.5	10.6±2.1
13	CP 005 (11 × 6) (9 × 6)	82.3±3.1	13.7±0.6	5.7±0.6	16.7±2.5	10.3±3.3
14	CP 0013 (3 × 2) (4 × 2)	88±2.6	13±0.0	5.3±0.6	14.3±0.6	15.1±2.8
15	BU papaya-1(1)(1×10)(13×18)	76.3±7.0	13±0.6	5.3±0.6	14.3±1.5	11.9 ±1.5
16	BU papaya-1(1)(11×10)(15 ×16)	82.7±4.0	12.3±0.6	5.0±0.0	14.7±3.0	15.7±6.6
17	BU papaya-1(1)(8×9)(13×14)	86.7±7.1	12±0.6	5.3±0.6	20.7±2.1	14.3±3.2
18	BU papaya-1(1) (7 × 6)(11 × 10)	72.0±6.6	12.3±0.6	5.0±0.0	17.3±2.1	7.6±1.2
19	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 4)	72.0±7.6	13±0.0	3.3±0.6	20.7±2.5	14.8±2.9
20	CP 0012 (7 × 2) (10 × 11)	83.7±6.0	14.7±1.0	4.3±0.0	23.0±3.0	20.8±4.5
21	BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 9)	73.3±6.8	14.3±0.6	3.7±0.6	21.3±1.5	23.8±5.9
22	CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9)	117.0±8.0	21.3±0.6	6.0±0.0	23.3±2.9	26.1±8.9
23	CP 001 (13 × 12) (6 × 7)	91.0±3.0	19.3±0.6	5.3±0.6	24.7±1.5	22.9±8.9
24	CP 0014 (11 × 2) (6 × 2)	92.3±5.1	15.3±0.6	4.7±0.6	20.7±4.5	23.7±8.6
25	BU papaya-1(1) (4×2) (5×2)	82.0±5.0	17.5±0.6	5.0±0.0	20.0±2.0	23.9±6.7
Mean		91.9±13.3	15.9±2.4	4.8±0.8	19.6±3.6	17.8±7.6
MSD		7.8	0.8	0.7	3.1	4.9

Data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (n = 10); MSD = minimum significant difference by Bonferroni test at 0.05 level.

Plant Girth

The average plant girth among the papaya lines was recorded 15.9±2.4 cm. Stem diameter or plant girth of papaya plants were recorded the highest (19.3±0.6 cm) in F lab (13 × 12) (6 × 7), and the lowest diameter (12.0±0.6 cm) in BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (13×14) (Table 02). Plant girth of the papaya breeding lines were recorded maximum in the first flowering stage. Plant girth of BU papaya-1(1) (2×7) was recorded 17.6±0.6cm and BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9 × 3) was recorder 18.3±0.6 cm. Faten and Bakry (2005) found that the average stem diameter at 10 cm above the soil was 20.67 cm in the studied cultivars.

Distance of Fruiting Node

Distance between fruiting nodes were recorded during fruiting stage. Distance of fruiting nodes were recorded the highest (6.0 ± 0 cm) in CP 001 (12×2) (11×9) and lowest (3.3 ± 0.6 cm) in BU papaya-1(1) (8×6) (2×4) breeding lines (Table 02). Average distance of fruiting node were recorded 4.8 ± 0.8 . Jamie *et al.* (2017) stated that some of the morphological traits were highly heritable and thus making selection easy. These are plant height, pulp thickness, fruit diameter fruit length and distance of fruiting nodes which were relatable to papaya fruit yield.

No. of Fruits per Plant

Average number of fruits per plants were recorded 19.6 ± 3.6 (Table 02). Among the papaya breeding lines the highest number of fruits were recorded 23.3 ± 2.9 in CP 001 (12×2) (11×9) followed by BU papaya-1(1) (2×7) [19.0 ± 1.0] and BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9×3) [17.7 ± 2.5]. The lowest number of fruit was recorded 14.3 ± 1.5 in BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (13×18). Kaluram *et al.*, (2018) showed that papaya genotype showed moderate to high phenotypic divergence for number of fruit per plant which increased the yield. But divergence in flower and fruit characteristics were more desirable for commercial utilization.

Yield per Plant

In this study the highest yield was recorded 28.9 ± 13.4 kg/plant in CP 0015 (3×5) and the lowest yield 7.6 ± 1.2 kg/plant in BU papaya-1(1) (7×6) (11×10) with an average yield 17.8 ± 7.6 kg/plant (Table 02). Yield of BU papaya-1(1) (2×7) was recorded 22.7 ± 8.1 kg/plant and BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9×3) was 20.2 ± 5.6 kg/plant. Yield of BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (15×16) yielded 10.6 ± 1.1 kg/plant. Kabir *et al.* (2001) revealed P043 produced the highest fruit yield (75.10 t ha⁻¹) and the lowest yield was observed in PO6112 (25.70 t ha⁻¹) in their study.

Fig. 11: Distribution of morphological traits of different papaya breeding lines.

Legends,

Rep= Replication, PH= Plant Height (cm), PG= Plant Girth, DFN = Distance of Fruiting Node(cm), FW= Fruit Weight, FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids.

4.1.2 Fruit Characters

Fruit weight

Average fruit weight was recorded as 0.9 ± 0.3 kg. The highest fruit weight was recorded as 1.3 ± 0.6 kg in CP 003 (3×20) (9×8) and the lowest was 0.4 ± 0.1 kg in BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (13×14) (Table 03) and (Figure 11). Saran et al., 2015 showed that fruits of papaya had the maximum amount of variation among all morphological traits. Fruit weight reflect the yield per plant with fruit number. Chantorn (2013) reported that individual fruit weight ranged from 0.75 to 1.32 kg of papaya under study.

Fruit length

The maximum fruit length was recorded as 26.0 ± 1.7 cm (Table 03) in CP 0015 (3×5) compared to the lowermost fruit length 12.5 ± 0.5 cm in BU papaya-1(1) (8×6) (2×3) with an average fruit length was 18.7 ± 3.9 cm. Anitha *et al.* (2018) studied that the fruit was oval to round nearly pyri form or elongated club shaped having 15-50cm long.

Fruit diameter

The peak fruit width (42.8 ± 8.5 cm) was recorded in CP 005 (7×6) (4×6) compared to the minimum fruit width (27.7 ± 0.6 cm) in BU papaya-1(1) (7×6) (11×10), with an average fruit diameter (34.1 ± 5.4) (Table 03). Iamjud *et al.* (2016) found that the fruit diameter ranged from 22.2 ± 2.0 to 48.8 ± 4.5 cm in their experiment.

Fruit Pulp thickness

In this study CP 005 (11×6) (9×6) had the highest fruit pulp thickness (3.0 ± 0.3 cm) and the lowest pulp thickness (2.0 ± 0.2 cm) in BU papaya-1(1) (4×2) (5×2) with an average of (2.6 ± 0.4 cm) (Table 03). Anitha *et al.* (2018) conducted the study fruit pulp thickness in papaya and found that pulp thickness increased the flesh percentage of the fruit. They also found the fruit pulp thickness ranged from 2.0 ± 0.5 to 4.0 ± 0.2 cm.

Fruit Pulp Color

Flesh color varied from yellow, orange, reddish to red depending on the papaya breeding lines. There was mainly yellow and red color of fruit pulp color in recorded papaya breeding lines. Saran *et al.* (2015) stated that papaya fruit flesh color may vary between yellow, orange and red color. Jaime *et al.* (2007) stated that immature fruit which was green in color contained white latex in more amount on ripening process fruits skin starts turning yellow-orange color to red, becomes aromatic, juicy and sweet.

Total Soluble Solids

TSS are important parameter of fruit quality. It states the amount of soluble solids in liquid. TSS value affects the taste of the fruit, because it can indicate the level of sweetness of the fruit. Average total soluble solids of the papaya breeding lines was recorded as 7.8 ± 1.2 (Table 03). The maximum total soluble solids (9.9 ± 0.7) were recorded in BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (15×16) and the lowermost soluble solids (6.1 ± 0.1) was recorded in BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (5 × 1). Iamjud *et al.*, (2016) found that the highest TSS value belonged to PML (15%) and the lowest being recorded in KD2 and SKK (11%).

Asudi *et al.* (2010) found a considerable variation in morphological traits in the germplasm of different localities in Kenya. Fruits of papaya showed the maximum amount of variation among all morphological traits.

Table 03: Mean performance of fruit quality traits of different papaya breeding lines.

SL. No.	Entry	Fruit Weight (kg)	Fruit Length (cm)	Fruit Diameter (cm)	Fruit Pulp Thickness (cm)	Fruit Pulp Color	Total Soluble Solids
1	BU papaya-1(1)(2×7)	1.2±0.5	20.0±6.2	32.7±6.5	2.3±0.5	Red	9.2±0.3
2	BU papaya-1(1)(22×9)(6 × 3)	1.0±0.5	20.6±3.5	36.3±4.0	2.9±0.2	Red	7.9±0.1
3	BU papaya-1(1)(22×9)(9 × 3)	1.1±0.2	20.3±5.5	31.0±7.0	3.0±0.2	Yellow	7.2±0.7
4	BU papaya-1(1) (8×9)(5 × 1)	0.9±0.1	16.6±1.5	32.2±3.8	2.7±0.1	Yellow	6.1±0.1
5	BU papaya-1(1)(1×10)(15×16)	0.6±0.1	18.5±2.6	31.0±1.0	2.2±0.2	Red	9.9±0.7
6	CP 005 (1 × 6) (4 × 6)	0.9±0.2	17.2±0.8	27.7±5.5	2.5±0.4	Yellow	8.7±1.5
7	BU papaya-1(1) (12×7)(4 × 3)	1.2±0.3	18.4±3.3	31.9±2.4	2.5±0.1	Yellow	6.2±1.5
8	CP 005 (7 × 6) (4 × 6)	0.9±0.2	18.8±2.7	42.8±8.5	2.7±0.2	Yellow	7.1±0.9
9	CP 003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8)	1.3±0.6	18.7±1.1	37.7±2.1	2.6±0.4	Red	8.2±0.3
10	CP 0015 (3 × 5)	0.6±0.0	26.0±1.7	39.7±6.0	2.9±0.4	Yellow	8.3±1.0
11	BU papaya-1(1) (6 × 3)	0.4±0.1	15.3±0.6	31.7±3.5	2.6±0.3	Yellow	6.6±0.3
12	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 3)	0.6±0.2	12.5±0.5	28.3±0.6	2.9±0.3	Yellow	7.2±0.3
13	CP 005 (11 × 6) (9 × 6)	1.1±0.2	13.3±1.5	31.0±0.5	3.0±0.3	Yellow	6.1±0.2
14	CP 0013 (3 × 2) (4 × 2)	0.8±0.1	22.0±1.0	36.7±4.2	2.7±0.1	Yellow	7.0±0.5
15	BU papaya-1(1)(1×10)(13×18)	1.0±0.3	22.6±1.5	30.0±2.6	3.0±0.3	Yellow	7.9±0.3
16	BU papaya-1(1)(11×10)(15 ×16)	0.7±0.2	18.3±4.6	32.5±0.5	2.7±0.1	Yellow	9.4±0.1
17	BU papaya-1(1)(8×9)(13×14)	0.4±0.1	19.0±2.0	30.7±3.8	2.0±0.2	Yellow	8.0±0.2
18	BU papaya-1(1) (7 × 6)(11 × 10)	0.7±0.2	13.0±1.0	27.7±0.6	2.0±0.2	Yellow	7.9±0.1
19	BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 4)	0.9±0.1	15.7±0.7	32.7±3.8	2.2±0.4	Yellow	8.0±0.0
20	CP 0012 (7 × 2) (10 × 11)	1.1±0.3	16.0±2.0	37.7±2.5	2.5±0.6	Yellow	7.1±0.3
21	BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 9)	1.1±0.3	20.0±2.0	40.0±4.0	2.8±0.2	Yellow	7.0±0.9
22	CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9)	0.9±0.4	18.7±1.5	38.0±4.0	2.8±0.2	Yellow	7.0±0.5
23	CP 001 (13 × 12) (6 × 7)	1.1±0.2	23.2±6.3	34.3±2.5	2.7±0.2	Yellow	9.1±0.1
24	CP 0014 (11 × 2) (6 × 2)	1.2±0.2	21.0±1.0	40.0±3.6	2.6±0.4	Red	7.7±1.2
25	BU papaya-1(1)(4×2) (5×2)	0.9±0.3	20.7±2.1	34.1±5.3	2.0±0.2	Yellow	9.1±0.1
Mean		0.9±0.3	18.7±3.9	34.1±5.4	2.6±0.4		7.8±1.2
MSD		1.2	3.9	5.5	0.4		0.9

Data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (n = 10); MSD = minimum significant difference by Bonferroni test at 0.05 level.

Considering several factors 10 papaya breeding lines were selected randomly for the assessment of anti-oxidant properties and fruit quality. Considering the morphological and fruit quality characters 10 papaya breeding lines was selected for biochemical studies.

4.2 Biochemical Characteristics

The ascorbic acid content, total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, antioxidant activity, lycopene, and β-carotene in ripe papaya fruits of ten selected papaya breeding lines were measured and showed in Table 04 and Figure 12.

4.2.1 Ascorbic acid

The variation of antioxidants is essential for improving new papaya cultivars with high antioxidants and carotenoids. The average of the ascorbic acid content was 48.4 ± 9.8 mg/100 ml (Table 04). Highest ascorbic acid content was recorded was in BU papaya-1(1) (2×7) (64.3 ± 6.0) and the lowest amount was recorded in BU papaya-1(1) (8×6) (32.7 ± 3.2). These were similar to other reports for papaya that ranged from 59.3–112.4 mg/100 g (Sangwanangkul *et al.*, 2010 and Souza *et al.*, 2008). The ascorbic acid level in papaya fruit was relatively high as compared to other tropical fruits. The ranges of ascorbic acid were 82.7 mg/100 g FW in guava (Sanguansil *et al.*, 2014), 26.9 mg/100 g FW in pineapple, 7.2 mg/100 g FW in banana (Hernández *et al.*, 2006), 67.0 mg/100 g FW in orange, 8.0 mg/100 g FW in dragon fruit, 5.2 mg/100 g FW in star fruit, and 4.1 mg/100 g FW in wax apple 3.9 mg/100 g FW in langsung (Patthamakanokporn *et al.*, 2008).

4.2.2 β -carotene Content

Generally, accumulation of carotenoid pigments in flesh fruits influence to visual color intensity (Yuan *et al.*, 2015). For example, tomato and watermelon with vivid red, orange and yellow flesh as papaya were reported that red flesh accumulates higher lycopene. In contrast, yellow flesh is abundant of β -cryptoxanthin (papaya), violaxanthin (watermelon) with almost lack of lycopene. Among the breeding lines, CP 005 (1×6) (4×6) reported the highest β -carotene content (11.8 ± 1.2 mg/100g) (Table 04) and BU papaya-1(1) (22×9) (9×3) contained the lowest β -carotene content (6.5 ± 0.6 mg/100g) (Table 04). Average β -carotene content was reported as (9.0 ± 1.2 mg/100g) (Table 04).

4.2.3 Lycopene Content

Quantification of lycopene content averaged 3.2 ± 2.6 mg/100 g, ranging from 6.4 ± 1.2 mg/100 g in BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (15×16) to 0.02 ± 0.04 mg/100 g in BU papaya-1(1) (8×6) (2×4) (Table 04). A previous report Chantorn, (2013) found the lycopene contents

in papayas as 3.4 and 7.4 mg/100 g. While Setiawan *et al.* (2016) reported 5.8 mg/100 g of lycopene content in papaya from Indonesia.

4.2.4 Total phenolic content

Now a days attention has recently increased in phenolic compounds because of their antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties. The average of total phenolic content was 29.4 ± 10.9 mg GAE/100 g. BU papaya-1(1) (11 × 10) (15 × 16) had the highest content (42.3 ± 7.5 mg GAE/100 g) and CP 005 (1 × 6) (4 × 6) had the lowest value (16.9 ± 1.3 mg GAE/100 g) (Table 04). Sanguansil (2012) stated that total phenolic content in guava could varies from 47.2 ± 4.0 mg GAE/100 g to 72.2 ± 5.8 mg GAE/100 g

4.2.5 Total flavonoids content

Total flavonoid content ranged from 27.3 ± 2.3 mg CE/100 g (BU papaya-1(1)(22 × 9) (9 × 3) to 11.3 ± 1.9 mg CE/100 g (BU papaya-1(1) (11 × 10) (15 × 16)) with an average of 20.0 ± 5.9 mg CE/100 g (Table 04). Recently, Spínola *et al.*, (2014) reported that the quantification of total flavonoid content of local and imported papaya in Portugal was 20.5 and 15.3 mg quercetin equivalents/100 g juice, respectively. Moreover, variability of flavonoid content is possibly affected by growing locations, harvesting, storage conditions, processing, and preparation methods (Haytowitz DB. *et al.*, 2013).

4.2.6 Antioxidant Activity

The highest antioxidant activity recorded 8.3 ± 0.2 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$ (Table 04) in BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16) and the lowest was 2.3 ± 0.2 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$ in CP 0015 (3 × 5). Average antioxidant activity was recorded 4.5 ± 1.9 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$ (Fig. 12). Compared to other tropical fruits, papaya had a medium level of antioxidant activity, similar to wax apple (6.2 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$), higher than pineapple (5.6 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$), jackfruit (5.5 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$), watermelon (4.6 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$), and coconut (4.2 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$) but lower than star fruit (23.3 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$) and guava (17.6 $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$) (Thaipong *et al.*, 2011).

Table 04: The content of ascorbic acid, total phenolic, total flavonoids, antioxidant activity, lycopene, and β -carotene in 10 selected papaya breeding lines.

SL. No.	Entry	Ascorbic acid content (mg/100g)	β -carotene content (mg/100g)	Lycopene content (mg/100g)	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/100g)	Total flavonoids content (mg CE/100g)	Antioxidant Activity (μ mole AAE/g)
1	BU papaya-1(1)(22 \times 9) (9 \times 3)	46.7 \pm 3.8	6.5 \pm 0.6	5.1 \pm 0.8	19.8 \pm 0.6	27.3 \pm 2.3	4.1 \pm 1.6
2	BU papaya-1(1)(1 \times 10) (15 \times 16)	57.3 \pm 3.1	8.4 \pm 2.4	6.4 \pm 1.2	24.3 \pm 4.5	27.1 \pm 3.9	8.3 \pm 0.2
3	CP 001 (13 \times 12) (6 \times 7)	42.3 \pm 3.8	7.7 \pm 2.5	1.4 \pm 1.3	18.8 \pm 3.3	13.1 \pm 1.4	7.4 \pm 0.9
4	CP 003 (3 \times 20) (9 \times 8)	46.3 \pm 3.2	10.8 \pm 1.8	0.5 \pm 0.2	17.9 \pm 1.1	21.9 \pm 2.9	4.8 \pm 0.2
5	CP 005 (1 \times 6) (4 \times 6)	53.0 \pm 7.0	11.8 \pm 1.2	0.8 \pm 0.7	16.9 \pm 1.3	16.8 \pm 0.5	5.4 \pm 0.5
6	BU papaya-1(1)(8 \times 6) (2 \times 4)	32.7 \pm 3.2	10.1 \pm 0.9	0.02 \pm 0.04	42.1 \pm 1.5	22.2 \pm 1.9	3.4 \pm 0.6
7	BU papaya-1(1) (2 \times 7)	64.3 \pm 6.0	10.1 \pm 1.1	6.2 \pm 0.2	37.9 \pm 1.3	24.9 \pm 4.1	3.6 \pm 0.5
8	BU papaya-1(1)(22 \times 9) (6 \times 3)	54.7 \pm 10.5	8.1 \pm 1.6	5.1 \pm 1.4	38.5 \pm 1.6	19.2 \pm 4.5	3.4 \pm 0.6
9	CP 0015 (3 \times 5)	43.0 \pm 4.4	9.6 \pm 1.5	1.3 \pm 0.4	35.6 \pm 8.4	16.5 \pm 1.4	2.3 \pm 0.2
10	BU papaya-1(1) (11 \times 10) (15 \times 16)	43.3 \pm 3.8	7.3 \pm 1.3	5.4 \pm 1.1	42.3 \pm 7.5	11.3 \pm 1.9	2.8 \pm 0.3
Mean		48.4 \pm 9.8	9.0 \pm 2.1	3.2 \pm 2.6	29.4 \pm 10.9	20.0 \pm 5.9	4.5 \pm 1.9
MSD		7.6	2.3	1.2	3.3	3.9	0.9

Data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (n = 10);MSD = minimum significant difference by Bonferroni test at 0.05 level.

Fig. 12: The content of ascorbic acid, total phenolic, total flavonoids, antioxidant activity, lycopene, and β -carotene in 10 selected papaya breeding lines.

Legends,

AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β -carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity.

4.3 Correlation coefficient

Correlation coefficients are used to measure how strong a relationship is between two variables. There are several types of correlation coefficient, but the most popular is Pearson's. Pearson's correlation (also called Pearson's R) is a correlation coefficient commonly used in linear regression. When anyone refers to the correlation coefficient, they are usually talking about Pearson's. Knowledge of the association between fruit quality traits and antioxidants will assist plant breeders in choosing which traits should be used for breeding programs and indirect selection. Largely correlated traits may indicate an opportunity to improve overall efficiency by reducing the number of traits required to determine the best cultivar to fulfil their requirement. Moreover, the knowledge of these associations will advise the breeder which traits should be viewed with caution in a breeding program.

4.3.1 Pearson's correlation coefficient for antioxidant properties and fruit quality traits.

A Pearson's correlation coefficient is the ratio between the covariance of two variables and the product of their standard deviations; thus it is essentially a normalized measurement of the covariance, such that the result always has a value between -1 and 1 . Pearson's correlation coefficient is the covariance of the two variables divided by the product of their standard deviations. The form of the definition involves a "product moment", that means the product of the mean-adjusted random variables; hence the modifier product-moment in the name. An absolute value of exactly 1 implies that a linear equation describes the relationship between X and Y perfectly, with all data points lying on a line. The correlation sign is determined by the regression slope: a value of $+1$ implies that all data points lie on a line for which Y increases as X increases, and vice versa for -1 . A value of 0 implies that there is no linear dependency between the variables. Several authors have offered guidelines for the interpretation of a correlation coefficient. However, all such criteria are in some ways arbitrary (Buda *et al*, 2010). The correlation coefficient forms the basis for selecting the desirable plant, aiding in evaluating the relative influence of various component characters on antioxidant properties. Correlations measure of the intensity of association between traits (Steel & Torrie, 1984). The selection for one trait results in progress for all characters that are positively correlated and re-progress for traits that are negatively correlated. Correlation coefficient analysis has been used by breeders to reveal a positive relationship. The breeding strategy mainly depends upon the degree of associated traits as well. Correlation is an effect size, and so we can verbally describe the strength of the correlation using the following guide for the absolute value:

Table 05. Absolute value and strength for character association

Absolute Value	Strength of Correlation
0.00- 0.19	Very week
0.20- 0.39	Week
0.40- 0.69	Moderate
0.70- 0.89	Strong
0.90- 1.0	Very strong

(Schober *et al.*, 2018)

Direct and indirect effects of several antioxidant properties and fruit quality were computed and presented in Fig. 14. Direct positive effect on yield of some characters indicated that selection of these traits is directly helpful for the improvement of antioxidant properties and fruit quality. Negative indirect effects of some characters the effects of such traits are indirectly affecting the antioxidant properties and fruit quality.

Pearson's correlations (Table 06 and 07) show the high positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.22$) existing in fruit weight with flesh thickness. According to Oliveira *et al.* (2012) it was possible to simultaneously fruit size and flesh thickness. Fruit size had a negative correlation with antioxidants and total soluble solids. For example, fruit weight moderately strong negatively correlated with antioxidant activity (-0.414), moderately weak correlated with ascorbic acid (-0.088), and TSS (-0.061); and very weak correlated with total flavonoids content (-0.028) (Table 06 and 07). These results indicated that selection for large fruit size may have a reducing effect on antioxidants and TSS in papaya fruit, similar to previous findings in guava fruit (Sanguansil, 2012).

Fruit pulp thickness also had a moderately strong negative correlation with antioxidants, indicating that developing new varieties with high fruit pulp thickness may have an adverse effect on antioxidant content (Table 06 and 07).

Ascorbic acid's relatively weak positive values correlated with both antioxidant activity (0.21) and total phenolic content (0.33) in papaya fruit. But moderately positive values correlated with lycopene content (0.54). Antioxidant activity showed a positive correlation with total phenolic content (0.15). Another investigator has reported similar result (Corral-Aguayo. *et al.* 2008).

Antioxidant activity revealed a positive correlation with total flavonoid compounds which indicated that total flavonoid were important contributor to antioxidant activity in papaya fruit. This suggested that the total flavonoid content could be used in screening indirectly for antioxidant activity in papaya since the evaluation methods are simple and do not involve the use of hazardous chemicals.

Lycopene represents the red color and β -carotene represents the yellow and orange color in many vegetables and fruits. A highly negative correlation was found between lycopene content and β -carotene (-0.43). The increase in the intensity of the orange-red color of the flesh lycopene content increases. Moreover, lycopene had a positive correlation with anti-oxidant activity (0.013) but β -carotene had a negative correlation with anti-oxidant activity (-0.054), indicating that red fleshed fruit pulp contains more antioxidants.

Fig. 13: Correlation coefficient between various characters in papaya breeding lines.

Legends,

PH= Plant Height (cm), PG= Plant Girth, DFN = Distance of Fruiting Node(cm), FW= Fruit Weight, FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids, AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β -carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity, NF/P =Number of Fruit per Plant, FY/P= Fruit Yield per Plant (kg/plant).

In the figure 13, illustration of Pearson's correlation coefficient had shown the ratio between the covariance of two variables and the product of their standard deviations; thus it is essentially a normalized measurement of the covariance, such that the result always has a value between -1 and 1 .

Table 06. Correlation coefficient between various characters in papaya breeding lines.

	PH	PG	DFN	FW	FL	FD	FPT	TSS	AA	BC	LC	TP	TF	AOA	NF/P
PG	.688**														
DFN	.519**	.411*													
FW	0.046	0.065	0.092												
FL	0.119	.392*	0.056	.370*											
FD	0.055	0.074	-0.052	0.306	.368*										
FPT	0.011	0.174	0.191	0.223	.471**	0.320									
TSS	0.140	0.074	0.018	-0.061	-0.034	-0.140	-0.233								
AA	.493**	0.356	-0.024	-0.088	0.029	0.000	-0.186	0.164							
BC	0.069	-0.115	-0.039	-0.146	-0.225	-0.121	-0.280	0.040	0.108						
LC	0.264	0.165	-0.064	0.135	0.014	-0.118	-0.006	0.231	.544**	-0.436*					
TP	-.523**	-.600**	-.508**	0.231	-0.053	0.135	-0.150	-0.037	-0.105	-0.019	0.230				
TF	.407*	0.337	-0.234	-0.028	-0.183	-0.029	-0.279	-0.238	0.333	0.037	0.313	-0.125			
AOA	0.340	.496**	0.116	-.414*	-0.005	-0.276	-0.250	.373*	0.210	-0.054	0.013	-.597**	0.154		
NF/P	-0.029	0.245	0.012	-0.064	0.102	0.191	0.110	0.050	-0.137	0.318	-.576**	-0.279	-0.155	0.129	
FY/P	0.063	0.228	0.060	.902**	.463**	.384*	0.287	-0.091	-0.143	-0.034	-0.082	0.071	-0.019	-0.298	0.313

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

Legends,

PH= Plant Height (cm), PG= Plant Girth, DFN = Distance of Fruiting Node(cm), FW= Fruit Weight, FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids, AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β -carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity, NF/P =Number of Fruit per Plant, FY/P= Fruit Yield per Plant (kg/plant),

Table 07. Correlation coefficients between antioxidant compounds, antioxidant activity, and fruit quality traits.

Characters	FW	FL	FD	FPT	TSS	AA	BC	LC	TP	TF
FL	.370*									
FD	0.306	.368*								
FPT	0.223	.471**	0.320							
TSS	-0.061	-0.034	-0.140	-0.233						
AA	-0.088	0.029	0.000	-0.186	0.164					
BC	-0.146	-0.225	-0.121	-0.280	0.040	0.108				
LC	0.135	0.014	-0.118	-0.006	0.231	.544**	-.436*			
TP	0.231	-0.053	0.135	-0.150	-0.037	-0.105	-0.019	0.230		
TF	-0.028	-0.183	-0.029	-0.279	-0.238	0.333	0.037	0.313	-0.125	
AOA	-.414*	-0.005	-0.276	-0.250	.373*	0.210	-0.054	0.013	-.597**	0.154

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

Legends,

FW= Fruit Weight, FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids, AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β –carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity.

Fig. 14. Correlation coefficients between antioxidant compounds, antioxidant activity, and fruit quality traits.

Legends,

FW= Fruit Weight, FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids, AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β -carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity.

Pearson's correlation coefficient had shown (Fig. 14) the ratio between the covariance of two variables and the product of their standard deviations; thus it is essentially a normalized measurement of the covariance of anti-oxidant properties and fruit quality that the result always has a value between -1 and 1 .

4.4 Path Coefficient Analysis

In papaya breeding lines path coefficient was analyzed for 10 characters related to fruit yield viz, Fruit Length, Fruit Diameter, Fruit Pulp Thickness, Total Soluble Solids, Ascorbic Acid, β -carotene, Lycopene, Total Phenolic, Total Flavonoids, Anti-oxidant Activity. Fruit weight was considered as resultant variable. Partitioning of genotypic co relation of different traits in papaya breeding lines are shown in Table. 08 and are discussed as follows:

The genotypic correlation coefficients were partitioned into direct and indirect effects by various yield contributing characters. Coefficient analysis showed that antioxidant activity had the maximum direct effect (9.313) with yield followed by total phenolic content (5.470), fruit diameter (4.023), fruit pulp thickness (3.325), ascorbic acid (2.550), lycopene content (2.110), β -carotene content (1.993) (Table.07). Fruit length (-2.681), total flavonoid content (-3.210), and total soluble solid (-4.879) (Table.07) showed direct negative effect but its effect to quality was positive due to high positive indirect effect. Considering the path analysis of various component characteristics with fruit weight and themselves, antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, fruit diameter, fruit pulp thickness, ascorbic acid, lycopene content, β -carotene content were important characters for improvement in antioxidant properties and fruit quality.

Table 08. Partitioning of genotypic correlation with fruit quality into direct and indirect components for papaya families.

Characters	FL	FD	FPT	TSS	AA	BC	LC	TP	TF	AOA
FL	-2.681	4.678	2.891	-0.869	-0.205	-0.878	0.104	-0.079	1.314	-2.099
FD	-3.118	4.023	1.967	1.588	-1.360	0.284	-0.752	2.455	1.407	-5.096
FPT	-2.332	2.380	3.325	4.027	-0.411	-1.364	0.070	-0.315	1.135	-4.839
TSS	-0.478	-1.310	-2.744	-4.879	0.920	-0.185	0.643	0.086	1.103	6.627
AA	0.216	-2.146	-0.536	-1.760	2.550	0.282	1.512	-0.747	-1.314	2.084
BC	1.181	0.574	-2.275	0.453	0.361	1.993	-1.498	-1.076	-0.008	-0.587
LC	-0.132	-1.435	0.111	-1.488	1.827	-1.415	2.110	1.389	-1.123	0.7645
TP	0.039	1.805	-0.191	-0.077	-0.348	-0.392	0.535	5.470	0.587	-6.543
TF	1.097	-1.764	-1.175	1.676	1.044	0.005	0.738	-1.001	-3.210	1.8364
AOA	0.604	-2.201	-1.728	-3.471	0.570	-0.125	0.173	-3.843	-3.843	9.313

Residual effect (R) =0.088

Legends,

FL= Fruit Length, FD= Fruit Diameter, FPT= Fruit Pulp Thickness, TSS= Total Soluble Solids, AA= Ascorbic Acid, BC= β – carotene, LC= Lycopene, TP= Total Phenolic, TF= Total Flavonoids, AOA= Anti-oxidant Activity.

Fig. 15. Path diagram (phylogenic) of fruit quality contributing traits of papaya breeding lines. Genetic resources must be characterized by morphological and agronomical traits in order to be useful for plant breeders (Martins *et al.* 2006). Cluster analysis was used based on standardized data to classify under investigation genotypes. The present study revealed the clustering of genotypes based on selected traits, which resulted in two clusters as shown (Fig. 15).

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY

A total of 25 papaya breeding lines were characterized and screened based on morphological, and biochemical parameters. The experiments were carried out during February 2020 to August 2021 and were conducted in the experimental field of Department of Generics and Plant Breeding and in the laboratory of Department of Agro-processing at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University.

Among the breeding lines, the tallest plant was observed in CP 001(12 × 2) (11 × 9) and shortest plant was observed in BU papaya-1(1) (12 × 7) (4 × 9). The highest Plant girth was observed in F lab (13 × 12) (6 × 7) and the lowest in BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (13×14). Distance of fruiting nodes were recorded the uppermost in CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9) and the lowermost in BU papaya-1(1) (8 × 6) (2 × 4). Among the papaya lines the highest number of fruits were recorded in CP 001 (12 × 2) (11 × 9) and the lowest number of fruit being in BU papaya-1(1) (1×10) (13×18). Supreme yield was recorded in CP 0015 (3 × 5) and nethermost yield was recorded in BU papaya-1(1) (7 × 6) (11 × 10). The maximum fruit weight was recorded in CP 003 (3 × 20) (9 × 8) and the minimum was in BU papaya-1(1) (8×9) (13×14).

Six parameter of antioxidant properties were evaluated of ten selected papaya breeding lines. The study showed significant genotypic differences among the papaya breeding lines. BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) showed the highest ascorbic acid content (64.3±6.0 mg/100 ml), antioxidant activity (3.6±0.5 µmol AAE/g), and total phenolic compounds (37.9±1.3 mg GAE/100g). BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3) contained the maximum amounts of total flavonoid (27.1±2.3 mg catechin equivalents/100g). BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16) showed the highest lycopene content (6.4±1.2 mg/100g) followed by BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7) showed lycopene content (6.2±1.2 mg/100g).

The Pearson's correlation coefficients were estimated among all the pairs of variables for papaya breeding lines. The yield was positively correlated with fruit weight, fruit length, fruit pulp thickness. On the other hand, it was negatively correlated with ascorbic acid content, beta carotene content lycopene content. Yield has a strong positive correlation with fruit per plant and weight per fruit, moderate positive correlation with fruit length, and the lowest positive correlation with fruit pulp thickness. Cluster analysis with dendogram divided papaya breeding lines into two clusters (Cluster A and Cluster B). Cluster A and B also was sub-divided into two sub-clusters.

From the correlation coefficient analysis in papaya breeding lines, positive correlation between yield and fruit per plant, fruit length, fruit diameter, total soluble solid, ascorbic acid content. From study we found that, fruit yield per plant expressed highly significant and positive correlation with number of fruits per plant, fruit length, pulp thickness and individual fruit weight, whereas the ascorbic acid content, beta carotene content lycopene content showed negative correlation with fruit yield per plants. But there was positive correlation among the anti-oxidant properties and fruit quality. Those characters like fruit weight, fruit length, fruit diameter, anti-oxidant activity, ascorbic acid, lycopene, beta carotene, total phenolic and flavonoid contents having positive correlation with each other will be useful as selection criteria for the breeders. From path coefficient analysis it was observed that the highly significant and positive correlation of anti-oxidant activity, total phenolic content, fruit pulp thickness, ascorbic acid content, lycopene content, beta carotene content respective had high direct and indirect effects but fruit length, total flavonoid content and total soluble solid showed negative effects. Considering the path analysis of various component characteristics with anti-oxidant properties and themselves, antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, fruit diameter, fruit pulp thickness,

ascorbic acid, lycopene content, β -carotene content were important characters for improvement in antioxidant properties and fruit quality.

Through the statistical analysis on several characters due to the contribution of various morpho-biochemical properties to the total variation and biochemical characterization, (a) BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7), (b) BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3) and (c) BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16) are recommended for high anti-oxidant papaya breeding line (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16: Selected papaya breeding lines.

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Findings during work, represents the measured quality parameters of different papaya breeding lines at each experimental run. The study shows a significant variation in antioxidant properties and fruit qualities in ten selected papaya breeding lines and this investigation clearly shows the potential value of selected papaya genotypes as new cultivars and their possible use in breeding programs for improving new papaya cultivars with high antioxidant properties.

- ❖ A considerable amount of variation was found for morphological and biochemical traits in papaya lines.
- ❖ Plant characters like Plant height, number of nodes per plant, number of fruits per plant has impact on the yield and quality of papaya. Fruit characters like fruit length, central cavity length, pulp thickness, individual fruit weight was statistically significant.
- ❖ Redder fleshed genotypes (BU papaya-1(1) (2 × 7)) and BU papaya-1(1) (1 × 10) (15 × 16)) had lycopene and β -carotene greater than other yellow-fleshed genotypes (BU papaya-1(1) (22 × 9) (9 × 3), CP001 (3 × 20) (9 × 8), or CP0015 (3 × 5). Fruit size had a negative correlation with antioxidants, indicating that selection for large fruit size may have a reducing effect on antioxidants. Over all the performance of the papaya breeding lines was good in case of antioxidant properties and quality characteristics.
- ❖ The correlation and path analysis showed that fruit weight, fruit length, fruit diameter, anti-oxidant activity, ascorbic acid, lycopene, beta carotene, total phenolic and flavonoid contents were the most important yield contributing traits because they showed highly significant positive correlation and high positive direct or indirect effect on antioxidant properties and fruit quality of papaya.

Recommendations

- ❖ Fruit quality contributing characters like fruit weight, fruit length, fruit diameter, anti-oxidant activity, ascorbic acid, lycopene, beta carotene, total phenolic and flavonoid contents will be useful and strong selection index for the plant breeders for their future breeding programs.
- ❖ Maintaining selected papaya breeding lines by crossing plants with better traits will be beneficial for yield and quality improvement.
- ❖ Further programs on assessment of antioxidant properties and fruit quality of papaya breeding lines could be made for proper maintenance and release new variety of papaya.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I. Nutrition values of papaya.

Nutrient	Value- USDA Nutrient database	Nutrient	Value- USDA Nutrient database
Water	88.83 g	Calcium	24 mg
Energy	163 kJ/39 kcal	Magnesium	10 mg
Protein	0.61 g	Iron	0.1 mg
Fat	0.14 g	Zinc	0.07 mg
Carbohydrate (total)	9.18 g	Beta-carotene	276 µg
Carbohydrate (sugar)	5.9 g	Thiamin	0.027 mg
Dietary fiber	1.8 g	Riboflavin	0.032 mg
Cholesterol	Nil	Niacin	0.338 mg
Sodium	3 mg	Vitamin C	61.8 mg
Potassium	257 mg	Vitamin A Eq	150 µg

Source: USDA national nutrient database for reference (2006)

Appendix II. Weather condition (rain) of gazipur, Bangladesh

Gazipur, Bangladesh weather Average			
Month	Day	Night	Rain Days
January	27°C	18°C	0
February	30°C	21°C	1
March	33°C	24°C	2
April	34°C	27°C	8
May	34°C	28°C	16
June	33°C	28°C	20
July	31°C	27°C	25
August	31°C	27°C	22
September	31°C	27°C	19
October	31°C	25°C	10
November	30°C	22°C	2
December	27°C	19°C	1

Source: World weather online (2020)